

DIGITAL AND PRINTED BIBLE: READING EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study project is to investigate and compare the reading experience that Christians have when using digital and paper versions of the Bible. It is essential, given the proliferation of digital versions of the Bible, to investigate if the format of the Bible in question has an impact on the way readers interact with the text. The research will make use of a combination of methodologies, such as questionnaires and in-person interviews, to collect data on aspects such as the rate of reading, the level of comprehension achieved, and the emotional connection felt to the material. The findings will shed considerable light on the manner in which Christians read and interact with the Bible, as well as on the question of whether or not there are material distinctions between the printed and digital versions of the text. The findings will be useful for publishing companies, educational institutions, and individuals who consult the Bible for either spiritual or personal reasons.

Keywords: Digital Bibles, Printed Bibles, Christianity and Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

The Bible is an important religious text for millions of people around the world. Traditionally, it has been read in a printed format, with physical copies of the text passed down through generations. However, with the increasing availability and convenience of digital devices, many people now also read the Bible in a digital format. This raises important questions about whether the reading experience of the Bible differs between the digital and printed formats.

The purpose of this research project is to explore and compare the reading experience of digital and printed Bibles among Christians. The study will use a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and interviews, to gather data on various factors that may influence the reading experience, such as reading speed, comprehension, and emotional connection to the text.

Understanding how the digital format affects the reading experience of the Bible is important for several reasons. Firstly, it can inform the design and production of digital Bibles, ensuring that they are optimized for the best reading experience. Secondly, it can help educators and individuals who use the Bible for religious or personal purposes to make informed decisions about which format to use. Finally, it can provide valuable insights into how Christians engage with and interpret the text, which has important implications for religious and cultural practices.

‘How might one approach reading the Bible via a digital device instead of a printed one?’¹

In the midst of my morning coffee break, this inquiry halted me in my tracks. The *War Cry* recently published an article about the Durham-based research group CODEC, which investigates the intersection of digital technology and religious belief.²

This paper aims to investigate what it means to read the Bible digitally and determine whether there are any notable variations from reading it in print. What advantages and risks come with using digital technology to read the Bible? How might the Bible itself offer guidance on how to use this technology wisely? Can a book that is so old offer any insight into how we access Scripture now via iPads, Kindles, applications, and the internet? I must now own my personal bias: I have always loved books and would typically chose print over digital. Because of this, I had some reservations about digital reading when I began this investigation, but I came to a more upbeat conclusion than I had anticipated.

I'm going to provide an overview of the most recent digital reading studies in order to investigate this topic. The backdrop to the current condition of the developing field of study into digital Bible reading will be provided by this. I'll then take into account the findings of my own investigation, which are grounded in my framework of theological education. I will show how the findings of a qualitative case study I conducted on Salvation Army cadets (ministerial trainees) and their usage of print and digital Bibles relate to the earlier study on digital Bible reading. Theological meditation on how the Bible itself encourages its readers to approach it makes up the dissertation's final section. How might this influence our thoughts toward reading the Bible online? How may this facilitate Bible reading for Christians in a connected world?

¹ The Salvation Army, ‘ReSearch Engine’, *The War Cry*, 17 June 2017, 8-11, p. 10.

² *The CODEC Research Centre for Digital Technology* <<https://www.dur.ac.uk/codec/>> [Accessed 22 May 2018].

During this research, I came to the long-overdue insight that print books are a type of technology that has altered how people access the Bible. They are not simply neutral, in the same way that digital Bibles are not neutral. It's only that books are so pervasive that their methods of influence are rarely questioned. Douglas Adams proposed that there are three stages of technology: first, the technology that exists when you are born, which is considered normal; second, the technology that is invented before you are thirty, which is perceived as creative and exciting; and third, the technology that is invented 'after you're thirty (and) is against the natural order of things and the beginning of the end of civilization as we know it until it's been around for about ten years when it grazes the ground'.³ This was referring to the introduction of the internet, but it may be used to any type of technology. Those of us who are not digital natives may be skeptical of e-books and Bible apps, and the print technology we have grown up with is our "normal." However, print is a technology, and the fifteenth-century print revolution had a huge impact on how the Bible is read today.

The printing press ushered in a cultural shift that resulted in the abundance of books and Bibles. This, in turn, changed access to the Scriptures as more people learned to read and Bibles became more affordable and common in households. In the years thereafter, Bible reading has become increasingly private and intimate in the Western culture, influencing how Christians live out their faith. Pelikan argues that:

“The availability of printed Bibles in common people's languages contributed to what has been dubbed the "Copernican Revolution" in the history of spirituality. ...There was certainly a symbiotic relationship between laity literacy, Protestant piety, and Bible reading”.

People started taking their own Bibles to church by the late nineteenth century, as Bibles got smaller, more affordable, and more widely available, keeping notes and following sermon texts.⁴

Today, it is reasonable to assume that the majority of Western Christians are literate and own at least one personal copy of the Bible. Personal devotions and Bible readings are encouraged by churches to enhance Sunday teaching and preaching. There is a sizable market for devotional books and internet apps, providing a plethora of personalised options. Bibles are available in many versions, colors, and at various periods of life.

Hipps also claims that the printed Bible gradually shifted spirituality away from the communal and toward a more individualized attitude.⁵ He warns of the danger of private Bible reading leading to a preference for individual spiritual exercises above social discipleship.⁶ The emphasis can be 'all about me' as I focus on my own spiritual journey and my personal quiet time apart

³ Douglas Adams, *How to Stop Worrying and Learn to Love the Internet* <<http://www.douglasadams.com/dna/19990901-00-a.html>> [Accessed 20 February 2019].

⁴ John Dyer, *From the Garden to the City: The redeeming and corrupting power of technology* (Grand Rapids: Kregel Publications, 2011), p. 24.

⁵ Hipps, p. 53.

⁶ Hipps, p. 54.

from the rest of my Christian family. A dominant culture that promotes personal fulfillment reinforces this propensity toward individualization. Individual reading, however, can and does have a good impact: where would the Reformation have been if Martin Luther had not studied the book of Romans?

The printing press ushered in new communication paradigms, which altered how information is communicated, thoughts are processed, and spirituality is practiced. Now that the digital revolution is having a comparable effect, it seems timely to investigate what difference reading digital Bibles might make.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Early Experiments with Digital Reading

Michael Hart founded Project Gutenberg in 1971. Beginning with *The Declaration of Independence*, he digitized public domain books and texts, making them available to everyone with a computer.⁷ Today, Project Gutenberg has 59,100 digitized manuscripts in 68 languages in a variety of digital forms.⁸

Digital reading has evolved beyond recognition in the years since. Reading modes have evolved from reading on a desktop computer to reading on laptops and other portable devices. The first handheld e-book reader was produced in 1997, Sony's first e-reader using e-ink technology was released in 2004, and Amazon's Kindle was debuted in 2007, the same year as the first iPhone. The iPad had its debut in 2010.⁹ Access to digital has become simpler and more commonplace.

Digital reading is defined as the "process of extracting meaning from a digitally formatted text." The first significant review of digital reading research was conducted in 1992, and research has continued ever since.¹⁰ Singer and Alexander conducted a twenty-five year evaluation of research, and Delgado and others conducted a seventeen year review.¹¹ Whole research networks have arisen, probably most notably E-READ, in which 180 scholars from 33 nations study the 'effects and repercussions' of digital reading.¹² The work of three authors, in particular, has helped to bring research into the public eye. *The Shallows* by Nicholas Carr contrasts with

⁷ Project Gutenberg, *About* <<http://www.gutenberg.org/wiki/Gutenberg:About>> [Accessed 31 March 2019].

⁸ Project Gutenberg, *Online Book Catalog - Overview*, <<http://www.gutenberg.org/catalog/>> [Accessed 31 March 2019].

⁹ Bob Burnham, *What's an E-book?* (Bloomburg, TX: Continuum Books) <<https://www.continuumbooks.com/whats-an-ebook/>>; [Accessed 15 March 2019]; 'E-book Timeline', *Guardian*, 03 January 2002 <<https://www.theguardian.com/books/2002/jan/03/ebooks.technology>> [Accessed 15 March 2019]; Charles Arthur, 'The History of Smartphones: Timeline', *Guardian*, 04 January 2012 <<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2012/jan/24/smartphones-timeline>> [Accessed 15 March 2019].

¹⁰ Andrew Dillon, 'Reading From Paper Versus Screens: A critical review of the empirical literature', *Ergonomics*, 35 (1992), 1297-1326.

¹¹ Lauren M. Singer & Patricia A. Alexander, 'Reading Across Mediums: Effects of reading digital and print texts on comprehension and calibration', *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 85 (2017), 155-172; Pablo Delgado and others, 'Don't Throw Away Your Printed Books: A meta-analysis on the effects of reading media on reading comprehension', *Educational Research Review* 25 (2018), 23-38.

¹² E-Read, *What is E-Read?* <<http://www.ereadcost.eu/>> [Accessed 3 August 2018].

Naomi Baron's *Words Onscreen* and Maryanne Wolf's *Reader Come Home*, which take a more favorable, if still critical, view on digital reading.¹³

Physicality

A physical book has an aura about it. The reader feels the weight of the book, smells the pages, and can see how far they have progressed in the book by the placement of a bookmark. They recall certain portions by aligning themselves with a dog-eared page or a coffee stain. These visual-spatial indicators constitute the recurrence technology,¹⁴ or the capacity to check what has been read by returning to a precise point in the text.¹⁴ Not only that, but the reader can see how far they have read and how much remains to be read: the book has its own 'more visible topography,' making it 'easier to build a coherent mental map of the text.'¹⁵ Reading a physical book may be 'less stressful intellectually' since the reader is visually and spatially aware of where they are in a text.¹⁶ Tanner goes so far as to say that 'print books are still the best adapted to the visual, cognitive, and metacognitive requirements of the reading brain' because of their physical qualities.¹⁷ These characteristics include the ability to annotate and flick back and forth between portions.

Reading a physical book requires the use of the entire body, not just the eyes. Spatial awareness is an important aspect of 'haptic' reading,¹⁸ which is concerned with 'the sensation of touch, particularly [...] the perception and manipulation of objects'.¹⁹ The ability to traverse a printed book using several senses is part of the enjoyable experience of reading. Digital reading, on the other hand, has significantly less haptic or tactile quality. An e-reader detects no weight difference between *War and Peace* and a much thinner volume. This 'haptic dissonance' influences the reading experience.²⁰ Although symbols and page numbers represent progress in a digital book, there is a completely distinct tangible sense of progression than in a paper book. It's difficult to turn back and forth to check details, and while annotation is possible, it's not the same as slapping a post-it note on a page or scribbling in a margin with a pencil. Technology has

¹³ Naomi Baron, *Words Onscreen: The fate of reading in a digital world* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015); Nicholas Carr, *The Shallows: How the internet is changing the way we think, read and remember* (London: Atlantic Books, 2010); Maryanne Wolf, *Reader Come Home: The reading brain in a digital world* (New York: HarperCollins, 2018).

¹⁴ Andrew Piper, *Book Was There: Reading in electronic times* (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2013), p. 54; see also Baron, *Words*, p. xi.

¹⁵ Ferris Jabr, 'The Reading Brain in the Digital Age: The Science of Paper versus Screens', <<https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/reading-paper-screens/>> *Scientific American*, 11 April 2013 [Accessed 18 June 2018], (para 11 of 31).

¹⁶ Anne Mangen, Bengt R Walgermo and Kolbjørn Brønck, 'Reading Linear Texts on Paper Versus Computer Screen: Effects on reading comprehension', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 58 (2013), 61-68.

¹⁷ M. Julee Tanner, 'Digital vs. Print: Reading comprehension and the future of the book', *SLIS Student Research Journal*, 4 (2014), 1-12, p. 9.

¹⁸ Jeffrey S. Siker, *Liquid Scripture: The Bible in a digital world* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), p. 62.

¹⁹ Angus Stevenson, ed., *Oxford Dictionary of English*, 3rd edn (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015) p. 790.

²⁰ See also Jim Gerlach and Peter Buxman, 'Investigating the Acceptance of Electronic Books: The impact of haptic dissonance on innovation adoption', *European Conference in Information Systems* (2011), <<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Investigating-the-acceptance-of-electronic-books-of-Gerlach-Buxmann/be70afda88b0a84b81f3b98424b372ef064ebb27>> [Accessed 30 September 2018].

advanced much since Dillon identified ergonomic issues with reading from a computer screen, but haptic reading remains difficult to recreate.²¹

Reading Comprehension

This lack of haptics has repercussions for the way we read. A recent study found that students viewed digital reading to be effective for comprehension, although this was only true for short texts and obtaining the core of a document. According to this study, pupils achieved deeper comprehension using print, especially with texts longer than 500 words. In such instances, navigation within a document's general topography is more important, and it is made more difficult by the need to scroll on screen.²² This supports Mangen, Walgermo, and Brnnick's 2013 study, which found that comprehension of a digital text was more difficult than comprehension of a print text because it is more difficult to map where one is in a digital text.²³

Skim Reading

Aside from the issue of reading content length and comprehension, research has proven that eye movement effects how we read since the 1950s.²⁴ Recent research has focused on how the eyes move when reading from a computer screen and discovered a particular pattern in those motions. Over a twenty-year period, Nielsen Norman Group studies validated an 'F-shaped' reading pattern, in which the reader's eyes go down the top line of a web item and scan the material in an F-shape.²⁵ This reflects how people scan a web page rather than reading it word for word; also, they often just scan the first page of an article or online page. This 'hyper reading'²⁶ is more 'information retrieval' than reading for pleasure.²⁷

Carr is concerned that, while skimming is a vital ability, it is becoming the "dominant mode of reading," and that scanning is becoming a goal in itself, rather than a means to an end.²⁸ His concern is that because scan-reading does not require significant focus, readers will grow less able to concentrate on longer, more challenging texts in the long run.²⁹ Wolf concurs, noting that

²¹ Dillon, 'Reading'.

²² Singer, Lauren and Alexander, Patricia A., 'Reading on Paper and Digitally: What the past decades of empirical research reveal', *Review of Educational Research*, 87 (2017), 1007-1041, (p.35).

²³ Mangen, Walgermo and Brønnick. See also Maria Gilje Torheim, *Do We Read Differently on Paper than on a Screen?* (2017) <<https://phys.org/news/2017-09-differently-paper-screen.html>> [Accessed 12 March 2018].

²⁴ Dillon, 'Reading'.

²⁵ Jakob Nielsen, *How Users Read on the Web* (Nielsen Norman Group, 1997) <<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/how-users-read-on-the-web/>> [Accessed 16 March 2019]; Jakob Nielsen, *F-Shaped Pattern for Reading Web Content (original study)* (Nielsen Norman Group, 2006) <<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/f-shaped-pattern-reading-web-content-discovered/>> [Accessed 20 February 2019]; Kara Pernice, *F-Shaped Pattern of Reading on the Web: Misunderstood but still relevant (even on mobile)* (Nielsen Norman Group, 2017) <<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/f-shaped-pattern-reading-web-content/>> [Accessed 20 February 2019].

²⁶ James Sosnoski, 'Hyper-Readers and Their Reading Engines', in *Politics and 21st Century Passions*, ed. by Gail E. Hawisher and Cynthia L. Selfe (Logan: Utah State University Press, 1999), 161-177, (p. 167).

²⁷ Peter Phillips, 'The Pixelated Text: Reading the Bible within digital culture', *Theology*, 121 (2018), 403-412 (p. 405).

²⁸ Carr, p. 138.

²⁹ Carr, p. 193.

this reading approach impairs one's ability to critically evaluate what one has read.³⁰ Wolf noted this shift in reading in herself and tested whether she could still read a printed book for an extended period of time. She was surprised to discover that she couldn't, and that it took deliberate effort to revert to a manner of reading she had previously thought usual.³¹

Distraction

Distraction is a similar concern for readers in the digital age. Reading on an internet-connected digital gadget involves avoiding interruptions from e-mail and social media updates, while hyperlinks operate as rabbit holes.³² This 'ecology of interruption devices' can result in a state of 'constant partial attention',³³ which in turn leads to lessened concentration, or concentration only in short bursts.

Liu's research, published before the advent of e-readers and cellphones, confirmed that reading online has altered how people read; he specifically observed reduced concentration spans in digital readers and how readily distraction occurs.

More time is spent on browsing and scanning, keyword spotting, onetime reading, nonlinear reading, and selective reading on screens, while less time is spent on in-depth reading and concentrated reading. There is also a decrease in sustained attention.³⁴ Similarly, Baron's 2010 and 2013 studies found that pupils reading onscreen had worse focus levels due to multitasking.³⁵ Students unanimously agreed that reading digitally makes it more difficult to concentrate.³⁶ Baron found that, while hypertext can stimulate creative thought, it also has the ability to disturb and distract. She saw a shift away from sitting still and reading the same item for extended periods of time.³⁷

Bilingual Reading

These research findings may appear overly harsh at first look. There are other advantages to consider, including mobility, search tools, simple font size changes, and the option to store multiple books on one device.³⁸ However, this has not been the focus of investigation. It is evident that digital technology has copied print rather than pushing reading in new directions, and it has yet to find ways to precisely replicate the print reading experience. Print reading continues to be the standard by which digital reading is assessed.

³⁰ Baron, 'Redefining Reading: The impact of digital communications media', *PMLA*, 128 (2013), 193-200 (p. 197).

³¹ Wolf, *Reader*, p. 99.

³² Martin L Kutscher, 'The Effects of Digital Technology on Reading', *Psychology Today*, Jan 15 2017 <<https://www.psychologytoday.com/gb/blog/your-childs-brain-and-behavior/201701/the-effects-digital-technology-reading>> [Accessed 25 July 2018]; Carr, p. 90.

³³ Wolf, *Reader*, p. 71.

³⁴ Ziming Liu, 'Reading Behavior in the Digital Environment: Changes in reading behavior over the past ten years', *Journal of Documentation* 61 (2005), 700-712 (p. 700).

³⁵ Baron, *Words*, pp. 88-89.

³⁶ Baron, *Words*, p. 89.

³⁷ Baron, *Words*, p. 174. See also Christine Rosen, 'People of the Screen', *The New Atlantis* 22 (2008), 20-32.

³⁸ See Baron, 'Redefining', pp. 199, 85, 63.

One intriguing line of inquiry is how the brain's structure adjusts to various reading modalities. Reading is not a natural human talent; rather, it must be learned, and the process of learning to read alters the way the human brain functions.³⁹ This 'neuroplasticity' is part of the brain's 'tendency to rearrange its circuitry in order to adapt to the most often requested activities'.⁴⁰ According to studies, e-reading stimulates different parts of the brain than print reading.⁴¹ It is now obvious that such brain modifications represent enormous prospects for problem solving and rapid thinking.

However, from the standpoint of cognitive neuroscience, the digital culture's reinforcement of rapid attentional shifts and multiple sources of distraction can stymie the development of the slower, more cognitively demanding comprehension processes that underpin the formation of deep reading and deep thinking.⁴²

Recognizing that print and digital reading have different capabilities for different functions has prompted a push for 'bilingual' or 'bi-literate' reading.⁴³ Wolf, for example, believes that youngsters should be educated to be 'skilled, adaptable code-switchers' who are proficient in both media.⁴⁴ If print is better for longer, more concentrated reading and digital is better for skimming, then, as Baron suggests, why not let 'form follow function'?⁴⁵ Mangen agrees that it is best to learn how to select "the most appropriate medium in a given situation and for a given material/content and reading purpose".⁴⁶ Instead of competing one type of reading against another, it appears that the secret is to play to the strengths of both.

Technology is constantly developing and improving, and as individuals grow more entrenched in digital culture, alternative tactics for digital reading are likely to emerge. Given the rate of technological advancement since Hart began digitizing books in the 1970s, it is reasonable to expect that the next fifty years will bring previously unimagined advances in the digital field. Meanwhile, employing multilingual reading as a strategy appears to be a sound strategy.

III. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DIGITAL READING AND THE BIBLE

Similarities between Digital Reading and the Bible

Physicality

There are essentially two ways in which physicality (or its absence in digital Bibles) is alluded to. One common motif is the iconic stature of the printed Bible, which is seen as a single

³⁹ Wolf, *Reader*, pp. 1-2.

⁴⁰ Laura Miller, 'Just Read the Book Already', review of *Reader Come Home* by M. Wolf, *Slate*, 16 August 2018 <<https://slate.com/culture/2018/08/reader-come-home-by-maryanne-wolf-reviewed.html>> [Accessed 01 November 2018].

⁴¹ Baron, *Words*, pp. 158-159.

⁴² Naomi Wolf and Mirit Barzillai, 'The Importance of Deep Reading', *Educational Leadership*, 66 (2009), 32-27 (p. 36).

⁴³ Wolf, *Reader*, pp. 168-187.

⁴⁴ Wolf, *Reader*, p. 171.

⁴⁵ Baron, *Words*, p. 133.

⁴⁶ Mangen, p. 66.

physical volume with great symbolic value.⁴⁷ The book's binding perpetuates the idea that 'these documents *belong* together, reinforced by uniform typography, page layout, and consecutive page numbering across the bound collection.'⁴⁸ The assigned symbolic value is greater than the notion of one authoritative book. Print Bibles attract a level of reverence and sense of propriety that is not generally found for digital versions, even though both forms contain exactly the same words. It has been suggested that the sense of iconic status is reinforced by the permanence of print versus the perceived ephemeral nature of digital,⁴⁹ with the physicality of print as a better reminder of Scripture's 'weightiness'. The print Bible has a tangible presence which digital cannot (yet) replicate but it is hard to articulate in concrete terms what that symbolic value is. Timothy Beal's term 'bibleness' is one attempt to convey this concept.⁵⁰

The subject of how people view Bibles on electronic devices is related to this.⁵¹ Does the fact that an iPad is "an icon of social media and a buffet of endless entertainment" lessen the Bible's credibility as a holy book?⁵² However, one may argue that including a Bible app in one's collection of applications alongside ones for banking, social media, travel, and fitness is an expression of a faith that permeates one's entire existence. Second, a print Bible can serve as a storehouse for mementos of the reader's spiritual formation, such as bookmarks, marginalia, and underlined or highlighted Bible verses. Hutchings argues that while a Bible app provides convenient digital access to the text of the Bible, it lacks the personal history and ownership that can give a physical Bible more symbolic significance.⁵³ McGlothlin goes on to say that there is something special about an inherited Bible that cannot be replicated in a digital format. He says that his grandmother's Bible, which was covered in scribbles that revealed her devotion to the Bible, is "one of the most precious treasures" he owns' he ever owned.⁵⁴

⁴⁷ Gunter, Ben, 'The App of the Gods: How much God is in my digital Bible?' <<https://www.bigbible.uk/the-app-of-the-gods/>> [Accessed 29 June 2018].

⁴⁸ Joshua Mann, 'Mobile Liturgy: Reflections on the Church of England's daily prayer app', *Heidelberg Journal of Religions on the Internet*, 12 (2017), 42-59 (p.45) <<https://heiu.uni-heidelberg.de/journals/index.php/religions/article/view/23768>> [Accessed 2 March 2019].

⁴⁹ Ian Paul, *Why We All Need Printed Bibles* [online blog] <<https://www.psephizo.com/biblical-studies/why-we-all-need-printed-bibles/>> [Accessed 29 September 2018].

⁵⁰ Timothy Beal, 'The End of the Word as we Know it: The cultural iconicity of the Bible in the twilight of print culture' in *Iconic Books and Texts* ed. by J.W. Watts (Sheffield: Equinox, 2015), 207-224, (p. 210). See also Katja Rakow, 'The Bible in the Digital Age: Negotiating the limits of "Bibleness" in different Bible media' in *Christianity and the Limits of Materiality* ed. by Minna Opas and Anna Haapalainen (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2017), 101-121, (Kindle ebook), location 2640.

⁵¹ Tim Bulkeley, 'Presence and Pixels: Some impacts of electronically mediated communication on Christian living', *Review and Expositor* 111 (2014), 36-56 [Accessed 5 May 2019].

⁵² Steve Burchett, *Why a "Paper" Bible is Better than a Bible App at Church Meetings* [online blog] <<https://ftc.co/resource-library/blog-entries/why-a-paper-bible-is-better-than-a-bible-app-at-church-meetings>> [Accessed 29 May 2018].

⁵³ Hutchings, 'E-Reading', p. 436.

⁵⁴ Brooke McGlothlin, *Why You Should Still Use Your Real Bible and Not Just Your iPad*, [online blog] <<http://brookemcglathlin.co/blog/2013/04/why-you-should-still-use-your-real-bible-and-not-just-your-ipad>> [Accessed 03 June 2019]. See also Rakow, location 2479.

Distraction

In contrast to modern devices, which contain distractions like notifications and social media, reading a Bible from paper doesn't take away from the experience.⁵⁵ As discussed in Chapter 2, the shallow nature of reading on electronic devices increases the likelihood of distraction. If a person is not deeply concentrating on a text, it is not surprising that texts, tweets, and pop-up notifications have the power to distract further!⁵⁶ Twitter, Facebook and Instagram notifications demand instant attention. Even websites dedicated to Bible reading are saturated with adverts and hyperlinks.⁵⁷ Notifications can be disabled, but few do. One of my students complained about distraction when reading from a tablet and was astounded when I suggested turning off notifications.

Jackson identifies a further facet of distraction in the context of religious worship. Despite the widespread acceptance of smartphone use in church, some congregants may feel uneasy if they see others reading aloud from their devices during worship.⁵⁸

Bilingual Reading

While print Bibles remain popular, the 2014 'State of the Bible' study reports an increase in Bible reading via digital media in the United States.⁵⁹ Given the proliferation of digital Bibles, this is to be expected. British Bible readers still prefer print over digital versions, according to the Bible Society's 'You and Your Bible' poll. While 63% of readers still prefer paper, 34% now choose digital.⁶⁰ For those born into the digital age, the percentages seem a little different: While 28% like digital media, 47% still favor print.⁶¹ However, there is no information provided for individuals who use both, making it impossible to give credence to the findings of the Barna survey.

However, the reviewed literature shows a concern for a hybrid approach to Bible reading, one that takes into account the benefits of both traditional and modern methods. Bibb, for instance, refers to Liu's research, which distinguishes between broad and deep reading, to argue that print Bibles are superior for contemplative reading.⁶² That "these two different media really serve two

⁵⁵ Gunter.

⁵⁶ Van Peursen, p. 57; Hutchings, 'E-Reading', p. 435; Kathy Brittain Richardson and Carol J. Pardun, 'The New Scroll Digital Devices, Bible Study and Worship', *Journal of Media and Religion*, 14 (2015), 16-28; Michael J Chan, *The Bible and the Internet* (Oxford: Oxford University Press) <https://global.oup.com/obso/focus/focus_on_bible_and_the_internet/> [Accessed 14 June 2018].

⁵⁷ Siker, *Liquid Scripture*, pp. 81-82.

⁵⁸ Griffin Paul Jackson, *8 Reasons You Should Bail on Your Bible App and Get Back to Your Hardcopy* [online blog] <<https://griffinpauljackson.com/2014/04/07/8-reasons-to-bail-on-bible-apps/>> [Accessed 28 June 2018].

⁵⁹ American Bible Society, *State of the Bible 2014* (Ventura, CA: Barna Group, 2014) <<https://www.americanbible.org/uploads/content/state-of-the-bible-data-analysis-american-bible-society-2014.pdf>> [Accessed 09 August 2019].

⁶⁰ Bible Society, *You and Your Bible*, p. 4.

⁶¹ Bible Society, *Digital Millennials and the Bible* (Swindon: Bible Society, 2018), p. 18 <https://www.biblesociety.org.uk/content/news/news_articles/2019_jan/Digital_Millennials_and_the_Bible.pdf> [Accessed 01 February 2019].

⁶² Bryan Bibb, 'Readers and Their E-Bibles: The shape and authority of the hypertext canon' in *The Bible in American Life* ed. by Philip Goff, Arthur E. Farnesly II, and Peter J. Thuesen (New York: Oxford University Press, 2017), 256-265 (p. 271).

different modes of reading," as Siker puts it, "is a consensus across the board."⁶³ Mark Bertrand expands on this idea, claiming that the two reading methods breathe new life into printed Bibles. Print Bibles may be utilized for meditation, for "deep, immersive reading," if digital Bibles and apps are helpful for Bible Study due to their search and study functions.⁶⁴

Bloggers are abundant on the web, begging with people to stick with the printed word and advocating the former.⁶⁵ This is not because they have anything against bilingualism; rather, they want people who read the Bible to gain an understanding of the text that they believe digital Bibles cannot give them. They acknowledge digital's convenience but worry about canon and history.

Differences between Digital Reading and the Bible

Convenience

Convenience is not one of the several themes reported in the research presented in Chapter 2 about digital reading. However, this is seen as a major benefit of digital Bible reading by bloggers and scholars.

Many options exist to make our lives easier. The first benefit is convenience: I don't need to lug around a physical Bible when I have a Bible app on my phone.⁶⁶ In fact, I can carry around an entire library of Bibles in a variety of languages on a single gadget without feeling the slightest bit cumbersome.⁶⁷ These are searchable versions: If I type in a term, the app will look it up and give me the results right away, much like a concordance would.⁶⁸ Many different sorts of reading regimens and reminders to read are available in Bible apps. It's simple to quote scripture to people as I read it.⁶⁹ Features that make Scripture more accessible, such as audio playback, adjustable font size, and lighted screens, are especially appreciated by the visually impaired, the dyslexic, and those with limited literacy skills.⁷⁰

Bible translators who want their work to reach its intended audience as soon as possible regard digital Bibles as the future. In countries where it is illegal to own a Bible and where books are expensive to print and ship, people can nevertheless have access to the Word of God through

⁶³ Siker, *Liquid Scripture*, p.111.

⁶⁴ J Mark Bertrand, "Are Bible Apps Destined to Purify the Printed Word?", *Comment*, 26 May 2016 <<https://www.cardus.ca/comment/article/are-bible-apps-destined-to-purify-the-printed-word/>> [Accessed 13 April 2019], (para. 11 of 25).

⁶⁵ For example Matthew Barrett, *Dear Pastor, Bring Your Bible to Church* [online blog] <<https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/dear-pastor-bring-your-bible-to-church/>> [Accessed 20 May 2018]; Jackson.

⁶⁶ Paul, 'Why'.

⁶⁷ Phillips, 'Pixelated', p. 405.

⁶⁸ David P. Murray, 'The Preacher and His Technology', *Puritan Reformed Journal*, 8 (2016), 216-221, (p 218).

⁶⁹ Jackson; Hutchings, 'Studying Apps', p.107; Alan Jacobs, "Christianity and the Future of the Book", *The New Atlantis*, 3 (2011), 19-36, (p. 32).

⁷⁰ Gunter; Hutchings, 'E-Reading' p. 434; Murray, p. 21; Phillips, 'Pixelated', p. 405.

mobile Bible apps.⁷¹ Digital Bible distribution is becoming more popular as the number of people with access to mobile phones grows.⁷²

Convenience has its detractors. After investing in a laptop or smartphone, digital Bibles become cheap, if not free, to download. That's why they're a nice perk for people who can buy cutting-edge gadgetry.⁷³ While having the capacity to search for a certain text is a wonderful convenience, it is not always the case that a digital Bible can be opened to that passage more quickly.⁷⁴ That is often dependent on the user's experience with a print Bible and the digital interface employed.

Context

In contrast to print Bibles, digital Bibles provide significantly less visual-spatial and paratextual indicators as to where a specific text is located throughout the canon. Academic studies do take this into account,⁷⁵ Christian bloggers have sparked most of the debate by urging believers to read their printed Bibles in church, arguing that digital Bibles fragment the text and obscure the Bible's larger narrative.⁷⁶ Concerns have been raised about the decline of biblical literacy, with some arguing that reading Scripture in print is preferable to reading it on a screen.⁷⁷ Some worry that people in the pew will become more "biblical illiterate" as a result of using digital Bibles'.⁷⁸ Also of concern is the tendency to quote texts out of context, as evidenced by the statement "Bible sloganizing [...] gains incredible speed and scale in the digital age"⁷⁹.

Readers who are not experts in the Bible still understand that the entire printed Bible is the church's scripture, and they recognize that there is more to the Bible than just the Gospels. The printed Bible makes the division between the Old and New Testaments, as well as the books that belong in each, physically obvious. Genesis and Revelation are the obvious bookends of the Bible. This is obscured on a book-listing app for mobile devices. A paper Bible, on the other hand, can be used for familiarization with its layout and contents through cross-referencing and page-turning.⁸⁰ Phillips argues that this is not possible with digital Bibles because readers cannot "make use of the kind of tactile and photographic reading strategies that book readers do

⁷¹ Neil Rees, 'Digital and the work of the Bible Societies', *Bible in Transmission*, Spring 2016, 21-23 (p. 21).

⁷² Bibb, p. 257.

⁷³ Murray, p. 218; Jeffrey Siker, 'Digital Turns and Liquid Scriptures', (New Haven: Yale, 2015) <<https://reflections.yale.edu/article/new-voyages-church-today-and-tomorrow/digital-turns-and-liquid-scriptures>> [Accessed 03 January 2019].

⁷⁴ Paul, 'Why'.

⁷⁵ Hutchings, 'E-Reading', p. 436.

⁷⁶ For example, Burchett; Ben Hawkins, *The Bible after Google: Evangelicals consider impact of technology on Bible reading* (Missouri: Missouri Baptist Convention, 2017) <<http://mbcpathway.com/2017/05/15/the-bible-after-google-evangelicals-consider-impact-of-technology-on-bible-reading/>> [Accessed 14 June 2017]; Mike Phay, *Four Reasons to Bring Your Bible to Church* [online blog] <<https://ftc.co/resource-library/blog-entries/four-reasons-to-bring-your-bible-to-church>> [Accessed 24 May 2018].

⁷⁷ Clive D. Field, 'Is the Bible Becoming a Closed Book? British opinion poll evidence', *Journal of Contemporary Religion*, 29 (2014), 503-528, (p. 508).

⁷⁸ Burchett; Barrett.

⁷⁹ Siker, 'Digital Turns', (para 6 of 18).

⁸⁰ Barrett, 'Dear Pastor'.

subconsciously" by, for example, flipping back and forth between pages to gain context.⁸¹ The printed Bible, Paul says, "naturally gives you the immediate context of a reading," meaning that you can see what comes before and what follows after a passage.⁸² Not because the context isn't there, but because it's harder to see, this is more challenging with an electronic media. A smartphone screen can only show a few words at a time, while a tablet screen can only show a few pages.⁸³ This makes it harder to see the larger picture and understand the Bible as a whole, and it also undermines the concept of context, both immediate and broader.⁸⁴

Kauffmann compares this to the use of analogue and digital clocks:

A digital watch just shows the current time, but a clock shows the progression of time. The Bible's page layout serves as a visual reminder of God's long relationship with his people. When reading a digital text, you can't see the whole thing at once, only the section you're currently reading.⁸⁵

A Logos employee who is less concerned with the question of context and more enthused about the potential of hypertext has been the only positive voice in the contextual argument I have encountered, saying that hypertext "allows us to see and explore the unity of Scripture its connections and themes and stories".⁸⁶ In contrast the majority agree with Siker and his concerns about 'liquid Scripture':

When the Bible ceases to be a physical book, not only does it result in a loss of tangibility, it also results in a textual world that is now virtually (literally, virtually!) watered down, so that the contours of the text become diluted and murky.⁸⁷

As more and more individuals in the world develop their digital literacy, this poses a problem for the church. It will be necessary to find and purposefully teach new methods of presenting and comprehending the larger context of Scripture.

Canon

The question of canon is related to the one of context. The Bible stands apart from other works because of its status as a comprehensive religious document with claims to authority and divine

⁸¹ Phillips, 'Pixelated', p. 405.

⁸² Paul, 'Why'.

⁸³ Siker, *Liquid Scriptures*, p. 92.

⁸⁴ John Bombaro, 'The Book That Isn't Really There: Digital texts and declining discipleship', *Modern Reformation Magazine* 22 (2013), 30-35 (p. 261).

⁸⁵ Richard A Kauffman, 'Holy Digital: The Bible on iPad', *Christian Century*, 01 May 2013, p.11.

⁸⁶ Ted Olsen, 'Hacking the Bible', *Christianity Today*, March 2014, 29-35, (p. 34).

⁸⁷ Siker, *Liquid Scripture*, p. 5; Robin Phillips, 'Scripture in the Age of Google: The digital Bible and how we can read it', *Touchstone*, July/August 2012, 40-44, (p. 44).

inspiration. For academics, the implications of a 'liquid' Bible on the concept of canon are a cause for concern.⁸⁸

In the wake of hypertext's introduction, Robert Fowler was one of the first academics to express such worries.⁸⁹ The question has remained even as technology has advanced fast in the years thereafter. Wright draws the conclusion that once "the Bible" or "the Scriptures" lose their basic relationship with the picture of a single tangible volume, their "authority" will certainly become increasingly ambiguous.⁹⁰ But while Siker is concerned that digital Bibles "can lose the historic function of a canon that has served for the last 16 centuries," there is some good news,⁹¹ van Peursen reflects that before the canon was finally recognized in the fourth century CE the Bible had no covers and this did not seem to harm the early church.⁹²

According to annual figures given by websites and applications, there is no shortage of access to digital Bible platforms, regardless of one's stance on the Scripture's liquidity. These reveal interesting information on app usage, Bible reading habits, and popular reading programs.⁹³ These numbers show that most people who read the Bible online only read a little portion of it. Jeremiah 29:11 and John 3:16 were the most-read passages from the Bible on Bible Gateway last year. According to You Version, Isaiah 41:10 was the most read scripture in the world in 2018, while Jeremiah 29:11 was the most read verse in the United Kingdom.⁹⁴ There has been an increase in the practice of 'comfort reading' the Bible, which Bibb interprets as evidence of the growth of a "moralistic, therapeutic deism",⁹⁵ whereby the great truths of Scripture about God are eschewed in favour of a narrower set of readings that are soothing and personally applicable.⁹⁶ Although it would be unfair to say that only digital Bibles promote a functional canon within the canon because no data exists on which verses people look up most often, it is fair to say that having a print Bible forces readers to confront the full breadth of Scripture. The more challenging sections of the text are still there, even if the reader chooses to ignore them. A paper Bible, as Hutchings astutely observes, enforces a specific order on the pages of Scripture by physically binding them together. [...] Reading one verse at a time on a mobile phone screen is far more convenient, and the urge to share verses through social media only serves to further foster this textual isolation.⁹⁷

⁸⁸ Several authors use the notion of liquidity or fluidity: Siker, *Liquid Scripture*: Rachel Wagner, *Godwired: Religion, ritual and virtual reality* (London: Routledge, 2011), p. 16; van Peursen, p. 55.

⁸⁹ Fowler, 'Notion of Canon'.

⁹⁰ Stephen I Wright, 'The Future of the Bible in Preaching', in *The Future of Preaching* ed. by Geoffrey Stevenson, (London: SCM Press, 2010), 84-100, (p.87); see also Trevin Wax, *When the Bible Becomes an App* [online blog] <<https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/blogs/trevin-wax/bible-becomes-app/>> [Accessed 06 June 2019].

⁹¹ Siker 'Digital Turns' (para 8 of 18).

⁹² Van Peursen, p. 52.

⁹³ Bible Gateway, *2016 in Review* (Bible Gateway, 2016), <<https://www.biblegateway.com/year-in-review/2016/>> [Accessed 09 June 2019]; YouVersion, *2018 Year in Review* <<https://share.bible.com/2018/>> [Accessed 9 May 2019].

¹²⁰ Bible Gateway, *Review 2016*.

⁹⁵ Bibb p. 262; see also Peter Phillips, *Are Bible Apps Changing the Way we Read?* [YouTube video], CODEC UK, 07 January 2019 <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mox4dQBazKA>> [Accessed 16/03/2019].

⁹⁶ Bible Society, *Your Bible*, p. 5; Phillips, 'Pixelated', p. 408.

⁹⁷ Tim Hutchings, "'The Smartest Way to Study the Word': Protestant and Catholic approaches to the digital Bible" in *Negotiating Religious Visibility in Digital Media* ed. by Miriam Diez Bosch, Josep Lluís Míco and Josep Maria Carbonell, (Barcelona: Blanquerna Observatory on Media, Religion and Culture, 2015), 57-68, (p. 64).

Bible links this with the issues of context previously mentioned:

As digital devices replace codexes, verse-by-verse reading has become increasingly popular. By eliminating unnecessary words and phrases, searchable and hyperlinked Bibles have the potential to become a canon of aphorisms, self-help, and rhetorical weapons [...]. leaving out the background.⁹⁸

The idea that the digital Bible is something we can control or master rather than the Bible itself being the final word on any subject is closely related to this.⁹⁹ Rosen worries that when we read on screens, we stop thinking like readers and start thinking like users. "instead of bowing down to a writer, you take charge".¹⁰⁰ The positive attributes of being able to cut and paste and to share verses in an instant online also serve this idea of mastery. Bibb even notes that the ability to compare translations and parallel versions can have the 'potential to destabilize traditional notions of what the Bible is and how it functions.' As ever this depends on the individual reader and how they approach the text. The question is whether the digital format promotes unhelpful attitudes, and this question has not yet been answered satisfactorily.¹⁰¹

IV. THEOLOGICAL REFLECTION

The long-term theological implications are as yet unclear, but it seems appropriate to reflect on what is currently known by considering how digital reading technology relates to what the Bible itself asks of its readers. This technology can be an excellent resource for the church, whilst simultaneously recognizing that technology shapes our lives in ways that we cannot immediately discern.¹⁰² This is not to vilify technology per se, but to urge caution about overenthusiastic adoption of new technologies without appropriate evaluation: 'Technology creates new options and requires us to think carefully about what is gained, what is lost and how practices both *reflect* and *shape* beliefs.'¹⁰³ Digital Bible reading reflects the idea that reading the Bible is valuable, and affords new ways of accessing the text. However, it may well alter the way the text is engaged with and how much of it is read. I have heard it said that as long as people are reading the Bible we should not worry about how Bible reading may be changed by digital access. Bible reading is definitely to be welcomed, however, I am convinced that church leaders and theological educators need to engage critically with digital technology in order to help congregations interact with Scripture in a healthy way.

Critical evaluation is key: in the questionnaire and focus group it became obvious that most cadets had adopted new ways of accessing the Bible without considering how it affected their

⁹⁸ Bibb, p. 262.

⁹⁹ Bombaro, 'The Book'; also Wagner, *Godwired*, p. 16.

¹⁰⁰ Rosen (para. 24 of 44).

¹⁰¹ Siker, *Liquid Scripture*, p. 84.

¹⁰² Robin Phillips, p. 40; Douglas Groothuis, *The Soul in Cyberspace* (Eugene, OR: Wipf and Stock, 1999) p. 23; Steven V. Monsma, *Responsible Technology: A Christian perspective*. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1986), p. 1; Dyer, p. 23.

¹⁰³ Giffone, Benjamin, 'Technologizing of Word and Sacrament: Deuteronomy 14:24-26 and intermediation in worship', *European Journal of Theology* 28 (2019), 66-77 (p. 72).

reading. They welcomed the convenience, portability and search ability, but had not considered that how they read might change. I imagine that this is replicated in many church settings, and, to be fair, had it not been for the War Cry article that sparked my interest, I might not have thought any further about the issue.

The foundation of this evaluation is the truth that whilst Christians live in eschatological hope, we still live in a fallen world. As such we need to live as ‘hopeful realists’¹⁰⁴ and wise sceptics who realize that something is wrong with everything in a fallen world, that things are rarely as good as they may seem initially, and that finite and fallen knowers can never accurately predict all the effects of a new mode of life.¹⁰⁵

In that sense, evaluating digital Bible reading falls comfortably within the Bible’s charge to believers to ‘test everything’ and ‘hold fast what is good’ (1 Thess. 5:21). Technology must be a servant of Christian practice, rather than setting the agenda.

This will help identify what aids and what hinders spiritual formation:

Christian spirituality must include an awareness of technology and media and their effects upon our faith communities and our world. That awareness enables us to engage critically with them and to integrate them into our lives in a way that aligns with an understanding of the call to follow Christ and to seek God’s kingdom here on earth. [...] Instead, it moves toward a genuine dialogue between technology and Christian beliefs, values, and practices in order to bring about sustainable, wise, and life-giving ways of life for individuals and communities both inside and outside the church.¹⁰⁶

In order to evaluate the degree to which digital Bible technology can aid us in this quest it is necessary to explore the Bible’s own view of how it should be encountered.

Value

The word of God is valuable because it shows the nature and character of God, recounts his deeds and his faithfulness to his people (Exodus 34:6-7; Deut. 4:34). God’s people are to ‘delight’ in God’s law (Ps. 1:2) which is described as ‘true’ (Ps. 18:30) and ‘perfect’, ‘reviving’, ‘sure’, ‘right’, ‘rejoicing the heart’, ‘clear, and ‘righteous’, ‘to be desired more than gold’ and ‘sweeter also than honey’ (Ps. 19:7-12). Psalm 119, the acrostic paean to God’s word, repeats the terminology used in Psalms 1 and 19 but delves deeper into the concept of the law as a treasure.

¹⁰⁴ Marva J. Dawn, ‘Technological Devices or Engagement in Practices?’ in *Proclaiming the Gospel in a Wired World: The 2001 Princeton Lectures on Youth, Church and Culture*, ed. Amy Scott Vaughn (Princeton, NJ: The Institute for Youth Ministry of Princeton Theological Seminary, 2001), 37-80, (p.46).

¹⁰⁵ Groothuis, p. 53.

¹⁰⁶ Campbell, *Networked*, p. 121.

The writer delights in the law (Ps. 119:35, 97). God's law is at the same time a source of 'longing', 'trust', and 'hope' (Ps. 119: 42-44,) and is 'good' (Ps. 119:39) and a 'comfort' (Ps. 119:52). He loves it 'more than gold.' (Ps. 119:105) It is a 'lamp' (Ps. 119: 130) and his 'heritage' (119:111).

In the New Testament the Scriptures of the Old Testament are perceived as crucial in the recognition of Jesus in his person and work as Messiah and saviour (Luke 24:27; Acts 10: 42-43; 1 Cor. 15:3-4; 2 Tim. 3:15). In addition, the Scriptures are 'useful [...] so that God's people may be proficient, equipped for every good work.' (2 Tim. 3:16-17) The New Testament follows the Old Testament pattern of shaping the lives of God's people around the God revealed in the text.

How do digital Bibles help readers value Scripture? Certainly, having the Bible available in a convenient form promotes the value of Scripture, making it available wherever we take our phones. The provision of easily accessible resources to unpack Scripture also contributes. Daily reminders to read the Bible can be an asset to those who might otherwise forget.

However, my research shows that the lack of 'bibleness' in digital makes for a felt difference in terms of a sense of reverence for the format, despite there being no intrinsic difference in the words accessed. Furthermore, digital is less suited than print to convey the idea that all Scripture is valuable, as only small parts are visible at a time. This makes it hard to visualize the entire breadth of God's revelation, and contextual reading can be compromised.¹⁰⁷ Although a print Bible can be read without reference to context, the reader knows there is a whole book to treasure; on a digital device this is harder to detect. Consequently, ministers and theological educators need to consider how to help digital users treasure the whole breadth of Scripture.

Listening and Community

Contemporary Evangelical churches generally expect their congregants to read the Bible as a personal devotional practice.¹⁰⁸ This is deeply ingrained, so it was surprising to discover that the Bible itself does not demand this of disciples and rarely commands individuals to read it.¹⁰⁹ In the Old Testament the concept of reading is generally reserved for leaders and priests who then instruct the people; they are commanded to make sure they are familiar with the Scriptures (Joshua 1:7-8; 23:6) and the king must write his own copy of the Book of the Law which he is to read all the days of his life (Deut.17:18-20). The priests are to read the Book of the Law to the whole community at seven-year intervals during the Feast of Tabernacles (Deut. 31:10-13).

This pattern continues in the New Testament. Timothy is commanded to read Scripture publicly (1 Tim. 4:13), and Paul calls for the reading of his letters in the churches (Col. 4:16; 1 Thess. 5:27). The people are expected to listen to what is read in community. Given the lack of literacy amongst the majority population in the cultures of both Testaments, this is unsurprising.

¹⁰⁷ Groothuis, p. 146.

¹⁰⁸ Evan Howard, 'Evangelical Spirituality' in *Four Views on Christian Spirituality* ed. by Stanley N. Gundry, 159-186, (p. 181).

¹⁰⁹ Stephen Kneale, *Treasuring the Word in a Non-Reading Culture* [online blog] <<https://stephenkneale.com/2017/10/05/are-we-in-danger-of-overstating-the-importance-of-quiet-times/>> [Accessed 25 March 2019].

This is liberating for people who struggle with reading and feel disenfranchised in church because they cannot easily access Scripture for themselves.¹¹⁰ Hearing the Bible read in church gatherings as a primary means of accessing Scripture is not a second-class option, it is entirely biblical.¹¹¹ This is a challenge to churches to remember to make the public reading of Scripture a priority, firstly because it is what Scripture commands, and secondly in order to be inclusive. It is also a reminder that the audio function of digital Bibles has a role to play: listening to Scripture is equally valid as reading it for oneself. Digital audio versions provide a bridge between current evangelical devotional expectations and personal inability to access a written text.

Digital Bibles and apps can also facilitate community reading, even if not face-to-face. The focus group discussion demonstrated how some cadets used digital apps to communicate with family and far-flung friends about their Bible reading. This can be helpful for those who cannot get to church due to work commitments, illness, or being in a place where they have no church.

Hearing and Obedience

The Bible is never to be read or heard for reading or hearing's sake alone. Throughout the Scriptures, the command is to hear and to obey, to know God better and to shape one's life and character around his commands and expectations.¹¹² The Pentateuch emphasizes hearing the word which leads to following God's decrees and commands. Deuteronomy, for example, enjoins the Israelites to keep the commands God gave Moses, to teach them to their children, recognizing the uniqueness of the law (Deut. 4:5-14; 11:18-21). The Israelites must 'give heed to', 'keep' and 'observe diligently' the commands (Deut. 4:2, 6; 6:1-8, 7:11, 12). God's people must make God's words the focus of their lives. They are not just to be aware of them, but they must obey:

Yhwh's teaching, for the most part, started as the gift of Yhwh's or of Moses' voice, but in due course became the gift of someone's writing that is thus available for reading to the people as a means of shaping their lives in obedience to Yhwh (Deut. 31:9-13).¹¹³

This theme continues in the writings, particularly in the Psalms. Psalm 119 encourages God's people to 'keep his decrees', 'walk in his ways' and 'observe your statutes' (vv. 1-8). The writer 'treasures [the] word' (v.11) in order not to sin. This is not an intellectual exercise: Israel needs to act according to the Law (119:59, 60).

The prophets are more concerned with how God's law has been broken by the leaders, priests and people (Isa. 24:5; Jer. 6:19, 9:13; Ezek. 22:26; Hos. 4:6). They indict outward religious conformity as worthless if it is not accompanied by an obedient heart, whilst calling God's people to repent and return (Hosea 14:1-2).

The New Testament continues the theme of obedience: James in particular is blunt: 'Be doers of the word, and not merely hearers who deceive themselves.' (James 1:22). Jesus consistently

¹¹⁰ Based on personal conversations.

¹¹¹ Stephen Kneale, *Five Ways to Dwell on the Word When You Can't Read* [online blog] <<https://stephenkneale.com/2019/06/11/five-way-to-dwell-on-the-word-when-you-cant-read/>> [Accessed 04 August 2019].

¹¹² John Goldingay, *Old Testament Theology II: Israel's Faith* (Downer's Grove, IL: IVP Academic, 2006), p.190.

¹¹³ Goldingay, p. 191.

warns against hearing but not putting into practice (Matt. 5:19; 7:24-27; Luke 11:28; John 5:39-40). He critiques the practices of the teachers of the Law and the Pharisees when they depart from the true meaning of the Scriptures (Matt 12:7; Mark 7:1-13).

The Epistles show reverence for the Old Testament, drawing on its themes, quoting it and reinterpreting it in the light of the coming of Jesus (Romans 1:1-5; Romans 3:2; 1Cor 9:8-10); they demonstrate the same emphasis as the Old Testament on the listening to the word that produces obedience and conformity to the ways of God now revealed in Christ. (Col. 3; Romans 12:1-2). The pastoral letters demonstrate the importance of the teaching of the word for the church. Paul instructs to Timothy to ‘rightly explain the word of truth’ (2 Tim 2:14), correcting, rebuking and encouraging ‘with the utmost patience’ (2 Tim 4:2).

How do digital Bibles help Christians shape their lives around Scripture? A sample of the digital reading platforms mentioned in the responses to the questionnaire shows slight differences in their self-understanding: YouVersion and Olive Tree indicate that life transformation is part of their remit.¹¹⁴ BibleHub is concerned with the ‘learning, study and application’ of the Bible.¹¹⁵ In contrast, Bible Gateway indicates that its mission is to help people understand Scripture but makes no specific mention of life transformation.¹¹⁶ The majority, then, see application and transformation as integral to their mission. It is clear that no app or website can make a person take steps in obedient faith, but it is good to know that there is an intention to help people shape their lives around the text.

Attentiveness

If the Scriptures are to be treasured and if the people of God are to shape their lives around them, a cursory reading or hearing of Scripture will not suffice. Psalm 119 is instructive, with eight particular terms for how to engage with God’s Word: ‘meditate’, ‘learn’, ‘treasure’, ‘delight’, ‘longing’, ‘cling’, ‘hope in’ and ‘observe’, words that denote deep engagement. In the New Testament, this deep love and commitment to pondering the law becomes focused on Christ: Christ’s words should ‘remain’ in the disciples (John 15:7) and believers should ‘let the word of Christ dwell among you richly’ (Col. 3:16).

How can digital Bibles help in terms of meditation? At first glance it is a medium that encourages speedy and superficial reading, and a constant barrage of notifications works as a distraction. The form of the technology militates against uninterrupted focus. It does not seem suited to the kind of deep engagement that the Bible commends. However, the convenience of digital means that in theory at least, the Bible is constantly available, and users can access it when travelling or waiting for the doctor, using ‘spare’ time to engage with Scripture. Apps exist to help Christians engage with *lectio divina* and Scripture memorization.¹¹⁷ Bible websites have

¹¹⁴ YouVersion, *Mission*, <<https://www.youversion.com/mission/>>; OliveTree, *About Olive Tree Bible Software* <<https://www.olivetree.com/press/>> [Accessed 10 August 2019]

¹¹⁵ Bible Hub, *About Us*, <<https://biblehub.com/about.htm>> [Accessed 10 August 2019].

¹¹⁶ Bible Gateway, *About Bible Gateway*.

¹¹⁷ A quick Google search reveals 137,000 entries on the subject of *lectio divina* apps: https://www.google.com/search?client=safari&rls=en&lei=0IIMXeaSBqLD8gKC5KyAAQ&q=lectio%20divina%20daily%20meditation&ved=2ahUKewjpruPkvTjAhVC6RoKHZZ7B_QQsKwBKAB6BAgBEAE&biw=1432&bih=734 Jar [Accessed 08 August 2019]. A sample of bible memory apps is found at Kaitlyn Garrison, *Five Apps to*

developed a plethora of reading plans which are free to download and Bible study tools are only a click away.¹¹⁸ The question is how they are used – and this has less to do with the software than with the person using them. Perhaps the first step is to switch off notifications to create an uncluttered interface. This, I feel, is the area in which most intentionality is needed, and perhaps this is a prime case for bilingual reading

CONCLUSION

This paper has investigated my initial question in several ways. It has compared and contrasted research into digital reading with research into digital Bible reading. The general research highlights the lack of physicality in digital books, as well as the marked difference between reading comprehension in print and digital; by its nature the latter leads to more superficial reading, particularly combined with the lurking distraction of the internet. Thus, researchers call for an integrated approach, favouring neither digital nor print, but rather bilingual reading in which the reading medium chosen is the one best suited to the specific reading task. Digital Bible researchers concur with these findings, but also take issues such as convenience, context and canon into consideration, with bloggers exercised about the former and academic theologians particularly vocal about the latter.

As I have reflected on my initial question, it has become clear that digital Bibles are read differently than printed Bibles. Print and digital prime the reader to read in different ways. This does not mean that print is better than digital or vice versa. Each medium has something to contribute to how the Bible is accessed today. However, just as print technology changed the way the Bible is read, digital seems set to do the same: in fifty years' time the digital Bible landscape is likely to look very different than it does today. This dissertation has given a snapshot of a specific moment in digital Bible development in order to contribute to the ongoing conversation about digital technology and faith. It has provided information and insights to stimulate further discussion about appropriate ways to engage with and evaluate digital Bible technology.

Based on my research, I feel that the following areas would benefit from further study:

- i. **Context and canon:** research into how to facilitate contextual and canonical awareness when reading digital Bibles. This calls for a multidisciplinary approach involving preachers, teachers and software developers.
- ii. **Online resources:** research into Bible reading plans and resources available online:
 - How to help readers to be discerning given the vast amount of information found online.
 - Evaluation of the major digital Bible providers and the underlying values of their platforms: how does the material they provide support their stated aims?

Help You Memorize Scripture [online blog], <<https://thebarefootblog.wordpress.com/2017/04/29/5-apps-to-help-you-memorize-scripture/>> [Accessed 08 August 2019].

¹¹⁸ For example: Bible Study Tools, *Bible Reading Plan – Read the Bible in a Year* <<https://www.biblestudytools.com/bible-reading-plan/>> [Accessed 08 August 2019].

- iii. **Ordinary Hermeneutics:** research could be expanded to specific congregations to ascertain the ‘view from the pew’, in a similar manner to Andrew Rogers’ research on Bible reading.¹¹⁹
- iv. **Theological Education:** I see a need for the development of theological education in digital issues, including digital Bible reading, in ministerial training.

The clock cannot be turned back: the digital Bible phenomenon is here to stay. Therefore, I hope that the Church will increasingly embrace the possibilities of digital, whilst finding creative ways to counter-balance its current limitations.

¹¹⁹ Andrew P. Rogers, *Congregational Hermeneutics* (Farnham: Ashgate, 2015).